

Prescription Writing Competency Evaluation in Dental Interns and Postgraduates: An Interventional Study

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ABSTRACT

Accurate prescription writing is a vital component of dental practice, directly impacting patient safety and treatment outcomes. Assessing this competency among dental interns and postgraduate students is crucial for identifying areas needing improvement and refining clinical education. This study aimed to evaluate the prescription writing abilities of undergraduate (UG) and postgraduate (PG) dental students and to determine the impact of a structured educational training program on their prescribing skills. A total of 450 participants, comprising 281 dental interns and 169 postgraduate students, were enrolled. Initially, all participants completed a pre-assessment questionnaire focused on common issues in prescription writing and were asked to write a prescription for a standardized clinical scenario. Later, an educational training session was conducted followed by post session prescription for the same case scenario. Both pre- and post-training prescriptions, along with questionnaire responses, were analyzed using descriptive statistical methods, with results expressed in percentages. Chi-square analysis before and after the session showed that postgraduates performed significantly better than interns in writing essential prescription and medication details ($p < 0.05$). Notable improvements were seen in documenting prescriber and patient information, diagnosis, drug name, dosage, frequency and usage instructions. Overall, postgraduates wrote more accurate and legible prescriptions. The educational intervention led to a significant enhancement in prescription writing skills, in order to maintain and build on these improvements, regular reinforcement sessions are recommended during various phases of undergraduate and postgraduate training to ensure sustained improvement and competency.

Keywords: Prescription, Dentistry, Educational intervention, Drug dosage.

INTRODUCTION

Prescription writing is a fundamental aspect of clinical practice, encompassing the process of documenting medication orders to ensure safe and effective patient care.¹ A prescription serves as a formal directive from a healthcare provider to a pharmacist, detailing the medication to be dispensed, its dosage, administration route, frequency, and duration. In the medical and dental fields, precise prescription writing is crucial to prevent medication errors, adverse drug reactions, and to promote therapeutic efficacy.^{2,3} In dentistry, the ability to write accurate prescriptions is vital, as dental professionals

frequently prescribe medications such as analgesics, antibiotics, and anti-inflammatory agents to manage pain, infection, and inflammation. Inadequate prescription practices can lead to significant consequences, including patient harm, increased healthcare costs, and legal implications. Studies have shown that dental students often lack comprehensive training in pharmacology and prescription writing, leading to common errors such as incorrect dosages, illegible handwriting, and omission of essential patient information.^{4,5}

The Medical Council of India (MCI) and the National Medical Commission (NMC) have established

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guidelines emphasizing the importance of rational prescribing and the inclusion of all necessary information in prescriptions. These guidelines aim to standardize prescribing practices, ensuring patient safety and adherence to ethical and legal standards.⁶ However, despite these directives, research indicates that many dental students and practitioners do not consistently adhere to these guidelines, highlighting a gap in education and training. This study aims to evaluate the prescription writing competencies of dental interns and postgraduate students and to assess the effectiveness of an educational intervention in enhancing these skills. By identifying existing deficiencies and implementing targeted training, the study seeks to improve prescription practices among dental professionals, thereby contributing to better patient outcomes and compliance with established medical guidelines.

METHODOLOGY

A study was conducted to assess the prescribing competence and perceptions of pharmacology training among dental interns and postgraduate students. A total of 450 participants were enrolled, comprising 281 interns and 169 postgraduate students from various dental institutions.

Ethical Approval and Consent

Prior to the commencement of the study, ethical clearance was obtained from the Institutional Ethics Committee (pr.395/IEC/SIBAR/2024). Written informed consent was acquired from all participants, ensuring voluntary participation and confidentiality.

Sample Size Determination

The required sample size was calculated using G*Power software version 3.1.9.2. Based on an effect size of 0.21, an alpha level of 0.05, and a statistical power of 95%, the estimated sample size was 449, which was rounded off to 450 participants.

Study Tool and Validation

Participants were asked to complete a structured, pre-validated questionnaire designed to evaluate their perception of the adequacy of undergraduate pharmacology training. The questionnaire was initially piloted with 25 students to test for clarity and

relevance. Feedback from the pilot group led to several revisions, including rewording of items, addition and removal of questions, and overall enhancement of comprehensibility and validity. The finalized tool consisted mainly of closed-ended (yes/no) items.

Prescription Writing Exercise

In addition to the questionnaire, each participant was instructed to write a prescription for a commonly encountered dental condition. This was followed by an interactive educational session that covered the principles of rational prescribing. The session emphasized the essential elements of a complete prescription and the importance of safe and effective medication use.

Evaluation Criteria

The completeness of the prescriptions were evaluated before and after the educational intervention based on the following components.⁷ Assessment focused on:

- **Prescriber-related components:** Name, qualification, registration number, signature, date, "Rx" symbol, and diagnosis.
- **Patient-related components:** Name, age, gender, and address.
- **Drug-related components:** Medication name, strength, dose and unit, dosage form, frequency, duration, route of administration, and special instructions if any.
- **Qualitative aspects:** Legibility and use of capital letters for improved readability.

Each prescription was assessed for accuracy, completeness, and adherence to World Health Organization (WHO) core prescribing indicators.

Post-Intervention Assessment

After the educational session, students were asked to write a second prescription for the same clinical scenario. Both pre- and post-intervention prescriptions were collected and compared to determine improvements in prescribing competence.

Statistical Analysis

Collected data were analyzed using descriptive statistics, with results presented in percentages.

Comparative analysis between pre- and post-intervention data was conducted using the Chi-square test, with a significance level set at $p < 0.05$.

RESULTS

Table I displays responses to seven questions. A high percentage of positive responses was observed for Question 3 (88%) and Question 4 (87.1%). In contrast, more than 60% of participants responded negatively to Questions 1, 2, and 5. Questions 6 and 7 yielded mixed feedback, with a slight majority indicating favorable responses (Graph 1).

Pre-session comparison using the Chi-square test (Table 2) showed that postgraduate students significantly outperformed interns in documenting several core prescription elements, including the prescriber's name, date, diagnosis, registration number, and patient demographics ($p < 0.05$). However, no significant differences were found in recording qualification, Rx symbol, signature, or patient address.

As per Table 3, postgraduates also showed significantly better documentation of essential drug-related information such as brand name, dosage form, dose, strength, and frequency ($p < 0.05$). No statistically significant differences were observed in documenting the generic name, duration of therapy, route of administration, or directions. Both groups had comparable results in terms of legibility, use of capital letters, and abbreviations.

Post-session analysis (Table 4) revealed overall improvement in both groups, with postgraduates maintaining a significant lead in recording prescriber details, diagnosis, and patient information ($p < 0.05$). No significant difference was noted for Rx symbol and patient address. Table 5 further indicated that postgraduates performed better in documenting drug names, dose, frequency, duration, directions, and showed superior legibility and clarity in prescription writing ($p < 0.05$). No notable differences were found for dosage form, strength, or route of administration. Additionally, postgraduates made greater use of capital letters and wrote clearer prescriptions overall.

Table 1 Analysis of Questionnaire

QUESTIONAIRE	Yes, N (%)	No, N (%)
1. Are you aware of new MCI /NMC guidelines prescription pattern?	167(37.2%)	283(62.8%)
2. Were there any questions in summative assessment regarding prescriptions?	172(38.2%)	278(61.8%)
3. Do you feel that undergraduate training has prepared you to prescribe?	396(88%)	54(12%)
4. Have you written a prescription previously for any illness?	392(87.1%)	58(12.9%)
5. Do you prefer generic name while prescribing a drug?	154(34.2%)	296(65.8%)
6. Do you prefer trade name while prescribing a drug?	276(61.3%)	174(38.7%)
7. Have you ever prescribed medication for special population like children, elderly and pregnant women?	280(62.2%)	170(37.8%)

Graph 1 Graphic representation of questionnaire

Table -2 Pre session analysis of Prescribes related components & Patients information

Prescribes related components	Results	Interns 281 (%)	Post Graduate 169(%)	χ^2	P value
Name of the prescriber	Yes	125(44)	125(74)	0.854	0.03*
	No	156(58)	44(26)		
Qualification	Yes	135(48)	115(68)	1.943	0.06
	No	146(52)	54(32)		
Date of prescription	Yes	130(46)	118(70)	1.764	0.01*
	No	151(54)	51(30)		
Symbol Rx	Yes	220(78)	160(95)	1.549	0.67
	No	61(22)	9(5)		
Diagnosis	Yes	135(48)	100(59)	0.657	0.02*
	No	146(52)	69(41)		
Prescribers signature	Yes	105(37)	155(92)	0.758	0.87
	No	176(63)	14(8)		
Registration number	Yes	135(48)	125(74)	0.432	0.05*
	No	146(52)	44(26)		
Patients' information:					
Patient name	No	171(61)	34(20)	2.931	0.87
	Yes	110(39)	135(80)		
Patient age	No	171(61)	34(20)	3.763	0.04*
	Yes	110(39)	135(80)		
Patient gender	No	176(63)	44(26)	1.576	0.01*
	Yes	105(37)	125(74)		
Patient address	No	156(58)	79(47)	0.452	0.57
	Yes	125(44)	90(53)		

P<0.05, * Indicates statistically significant

Table -3 Pre session analysis of Drug –related components & Other components

Drug –related components	Results	Interns 281 (%)	Post Graduate 169 (%)	χ^2	P value
Brand name mentioned	Yes	200(71)	95(56)	2.435	0.01*
	No	81(29)	74(44)		
Generic name mentioned	Yes	110(39)	110(65)	1.698	0.45
	No	171(61)	59(35)		
Dosage form	Yes	125(44)	155(92)	0.674	0.01*
	No	156(58)	14(8)		
Dose of the drug	Yes	135(48)	155(92)	1.589	0.03*
	No	146(52)	14(8)		
Incorrect dose mentioned	Yes	130(46)	110(65)	2.945	0.54
	No	151(54)	59(35)		
Strength not mentioned	Yes	65(23)	58(34)	2.872	0.02*
	No	216(77)	111(66)		
Frequency	Yes	135(48)	155(92)	3.654	0.01*
	No	146(52)	14(8)		
Duration	Yes	110(39)	130(77)	2.487	0.20
	No	171(61)	39(23)		
Route of administration	Yes	105(37)	100(59)	1.678	0.50
	No	176(63)	69(41)		
Direction for use	Yes	130(46)	65(38)	3.675	0.89
	No	151(54)	104(62)		
Other components					
Legible handwriting	No	6(2)	4(2)	2.656	0.76
	Yes	275(98)	165(98)		
Information in capital letter	No	146(52)	34(20)	2.898	0.45

	Yes	135(48)	135(80)		
Use of abbreviation	No	156(58)	104(62)	1.654	0.53
	Yes	125(44)	65(38)		

P<0.05, * Indicates statistically significant

Table -4 Post session analysis of Prescribes related components & Patients information

Prescribes related components	Results	Interns 281 (%)	Post Graduate 169 (%)	χ^2	P value
Name of the prescriber	Yes	200(71)	165(98)	2.117	0.02*
	No	81(29)	4(2)		
Qualification	Yes	210(75)	145(86)	2.456	0.01*
	No	71(25)	24(14)		
Date of prescription	Yes	200(71)	148(88)	3.238	0.02*
	No	81(29)	21(12)		
Symbol Rx	Yes	260(93)	167(99)	1.567	0.34
	No	21(7)	2(1)		
Diagnosis	Yes	175(62)	130(77)	1.879	0.01*
	No	106(38)	39(23)		
Prescribers signature	Yes	220(78)	167(99)	2.567	0.01*
	No	61(22)	2(1)		
Registration number	Yes	230(82)	155(92)	3.654	0.02*
	No	51(18)	14(8)		
Patients information:					
Patient name	No	61(22)	4(2)	2.432	0.02*
	Yes	220(78)	165(98)		
Patient age	No	61(22)	4(2)	1.768	0.01*
	Yes	220(78)	165(98)		
Patient gender	No	71(25)	14(8)	1.457	0.04*
	Yes	210(75)	155(92)		
Patient address	No	101(36)	49(29)	2.543	0.23
	Yes	180(64)	120(71)		

P<0.05, * Indicates statistically significant

Table -5 Post session analysis of Drug –related components & Other components

Drug –related components	Results	Interns 281 (%)	Post Graduate 169 (%)	χ^2	P value
Brand name mentioned	Yes	240(85)	125(74)	3.245	0.01*
	No	41(15)	44(26)		
Generic name mentioned	Yes	180(64)	140(83)	2.564	0.02*
	No	101(36)	29(17)		
Dosage form	Yes	200(71)	167(99)	1.876	0.56
	No	81(29)	2(1)		
Dose of the drug	Yes	230(82)	167(99)	0.453	0.05*
	No	51(18)	2(1)		
Incorrect dose mentioned	Yes	200(71)	140(83)	0.786	0.67
	No	81(29)	29(17)		
Strength not mentioned	Yes	135(48)	88(52)	0.324	0.23
	No	146(52)	81(48)		
Frequency	Yes	230(82)	167(99)	1.459	0.05*
	No	51(18)	2(1)		
Duration	Yes	220(78)	160(95)	1.075	0.02*
	No	61(22)	9(5)		
Route of administration	Yes	175(62)	130(77)	1.765	0.76
	No	106(38)	39(23)		
Direction for use	Yes	175(62)	95(56)	1.643	0.01*

	No	106(38)	74(44)		
Other components					
Legible handwriting	Yes	279(99)	167(99)	2.765	0.01*
	No	2(1)	2(1)		
Information in capital letter	Yes	230(82)	165(98)	2.921	0.03*
	No	51(18)	4(2)		
Use of abbreviation	Yes	175(62)	95(56)	1.067	0.01*
	No	106(38)	74(44)		

P<0.05, * Indicates statistically significant

DISCUSSION

This study assessed the prescription writing competencies of dental interns and postgraduate students and evaluated the impact of a structured educational intervention in enhancing these skills. The gender distribution among the 450 study participants, Females constituted a larger portion of the sample, accounting for 70.6% (n=318), while males made up 29.4% (n=132), indicating a female predominance. The academic level of participants, with interns forming the majority at 62.4% (n=281), followed by first-year (13.6%, n=61), second-year (12.3%, n=55), and third-year postgraduates (11.7%, n=53). In the present study, the assessment of prescribing knowledge and habits through a structured questionnaire revealed several noteworthy trends. A majority of the participants (62.8%) reported being unaware of the recent prescription-related guidelines issued by the Medical Council of India (MCI)/National Medical Commission (NMC), indicating a gap in the dissemination or integration of updated regulatory standards into medical education. Similarly, 61.8% of the respondents stated that they had not encountered questions related to prescription writing in their summative assessments, suggesting that this crucial aspect of clinical training may be underrepresented in academic evaluations. Despite these gaps, a substantial proportion (88%) of participants felt confident that their undergraduate training had adequately prepared them to prescribe medications, and 87.1% had previously written prescriptions, reflecting a relatively high level of self-assessed competence and exposure. However, only about one-third (34.2%) expressed a preference for prescribing drugs by their generic names, while a greater proportion (61.3%) favored the use of trade names. This trend raises concerns regarding prescribing practices, especially in the context of promoting rational drug use and reducing healthcare

costs. Moreover, 62.2% of participants reported having prescribed medications for special populations, such as children, pregnant women, and the elderly, highlighting the importance of tailoring pharmacological education to address the unique considerations required for these groups. The questionnaire feedback provided by participants offers further insight into the perceived value of their undergraduate pharmacology education. A significant proportion of students reported feeling inadequately prepared for real-world prescribing during their undergraduate training. These observations align with those reported by Shetty et al. (2016),⁸ who emphasized that pharmacology taught in a purely theoretical manner often does not translate into practical prescribing skills unless it is reinforced through clinical application. This highlights the importance of integrating prescription writing training throughout the dental curriculum in a stepwise and continuous manner, allowing students to apply and build upon their foundational knowledge through hands-on clinical experience. Our results are in agreement with similar research conducted both within India and in neighboring countries, reflecting a broader regional trend.^{9,10}

The pre-session analysis revealed a substantial shortfall in the interns' ability to complete critical fields in a prescription. Only 44% of interns correctly wrote the prescriber's name compared to 74% of postgraduates. Similarly, accurate entry of the prescription date and diagnosis was observed in just 46% and 48% of interns, respectively, versus 70% and 59% in the postgraduate group. These differences underscore a lack of familiarity with the practical components of prescription writing among undergraduate students. Such deficiencies are not isolated to this study; Siddarth et al (2014),¹¹ Varghese et al. (2018)¹² identified similar issues among dental and medical undergraduates in Kerala,

with incomplete documentation being the most common error.

In the pre-session assessment of patient-related information, 39% of interns and 80% of postgraduates correctly recorded the patient's name and age, while the address was noted by 44% of interns and 53% of postgraduates. These findings are comparable to those of Babar et al. (2014)¹³ and Baig et al. (2020),¹⁴ who also reported a higher degree of accuracy in documenting patient details among postgraduate participants. The positive impact of the educational intervention was evident across both groups, though more prominent among postgraduates. In the post-session assessment, documentation of prescriber-related elements saw a significant boost: 98% of postgraduates and 71% of interns correctly wrote the prescriber's name, and a similar trend was observed in recording qualifications, registration numbers, and diagnosis. Likewise, patient-related information such as name, age, and gender was correctly noted by 98% of postgraduates and 78% of interns after the intervention. These improvements validate the efficacy of structured, targeted educational strategies in addressing gaps in clinical documentation.

The assessment of drug-related components before and after the educational intervention demonstrated significant progress in prescription accuracy among both interns and postgraduate students. Initially, interns were more inclined to mention brand names, whereas postgraduates more frequently used generic names, reflecting a stronger commitment to rational prescribing. Following the intervention, there was a notable improvement—particularly among postgraduates—in the proper documentation of key elements such as dosage form, drug dose, frequency, and duration. Despite these improvements, issues like incorrect dosing and omission of drug strength persisted across both groups. Furthermore, directions for use remained inadequately addressed, with postgraduates showing slightly lower compliance in this aspect, indicating a persistent gap in patient-oriented communication. These observations are consistent with the findings of Ballalet al. (2005)¹⁵ and Wali et al. (2012),¹⁶ who also reported deficiencies in the completeness of prescription details among dental students.

Guzmán-Álvarez et al. (2012)⁵, reported similar findings, where interactive pharmacological training significantly enhanced dental students' understanding and application of prescribing principles. The use of simulated case-based scenarios and interactive discussions, as adopted in the present study, likely contributed to this enhancement. Notably, the use of generic drug names improved from 39% to 64% among interns and from 65% to 83% among postgraduates. Although an improvement was seen, this area still reflects underperformance, suggesting a bias toward brand-name prescriptions. This is particularly concerning given the global movement toward rational prescribing and cost-effective healthcare delivery. Other elements, such as route of administration and special instructions for drug use, remained sub optimally documented even after the intervention. Among postgraduates, only 77% correctly recorded the route of administration post-session, compared to 62% of interns. Dyasanoor et al (2016)¹⁷ also observed these components to be the most frequently overlooked in institutional settings despite training efforts, suggesting they require more focused reinforcement.

Qualitative components of prescription writing, such as handwriting legibility and clarity, are often overlooked in training but are crucial for preventing misinterpretation and medication errors. In the present study, the use of capital letters improved post-intervention in both groups, with postgraduates reaching 98% compliance. Legibility was nearly universal post-session, with 99% of both groups writing clearly. Karibasappa et al. (2015)¹⁸, also identified that poor handwriting and ambiguous abbreviations were common contributors to prescription-related errors in clinical practice. By integrating these aspects into the educational session, the intervention effectively addressed both the content and presentation of prescriptions. The analysis, both pre- and post-intervention, revealed consistent and statistically significant differences between the two groups, with postgraduate students demonstrating superior performance in documenting essential components of a prescription, including prescriber information, patient details, diagnosis, and drug-related data such as dose, frequency, and duration. These findings highlight a persistent gap in undergraduate training and emphasize the necessity of

targeted pedagogical strategies to enhance prescription writing competency among dental professionals. This is further supported by the findings of Doshi et al (2017)¹⁹, who conducted a cross-sectional study evaluating the knowledge and prescribing practices of dental students in India, specifically related to antibiotics and analgesics. Their study concluded that undergraduate students exhibited significantly less knowledge and confidence in prescribing medications compared to postgraduate students. The study has a few limitations. It was based on a one-time training session and evaluated outcomes over a short duration, which may not reflect long-term learning. The use of a standardized case scenario might not fully represent the complexity of real-world clinical practice. Additionally, the use of a closed-ended questionnaire and the study's limited geographic scope may affect the depth of insights and generalizability of the findings.

CONCLUSION

- The study showed that postgraduate dental students performed better than interns in writing prescriptions, both before and after the training.
- The educational session helped both groups improve in writing key prescription details like the prescriber's information, patient data, and drug-related elements such as dose, frequency, and duration.
- However, some parts like writing generic drug names, the route of administration, and the patient's address were still not recorded consistently and need more attention in future training.
- The session also improved writing clarity, including better handwriting and the use of capital letters, which are important for safe and clear communication.

The findings support the integration of regular, hands-on prescription writing training sessions into both undergraduate and postgraduate dental curriculum. Continuous reinforcement through periodic assessments, audits, and mentorship is recommended to ensure long-term retention and practice of rational prescribing habits.

AUTHORS CONTRIBUTIONS

All the authors have contributed equally.

CONFLICT OF INTERESTS

Declared none

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